

Projected and perceived destination image of the Lake Lucerne Region

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ABSTRACT

Tourists play an important role in shaping the destination image by posting their experiences on visual and audio-visual channels. Thus, it is increasingly important for a successful destination marketing strategy that destination managers know how their destination is perceived and whether this is aligned with the image they project. This comparative content analysis evaluates the potential gap between the projected and perceived destination image for the Lake Lucerne Region in Switzerland on Instagram.

From a database of over 10,000 posts, this study takes a closer look at 300 randomly selected user-generated picture posts and a corresponding number of picture posts from four destination management organisations using a classification system of 27 attribute categories to analyse the content. The results show that tourists and tourism organisations use similar attributes to depict the destination image. The results shed light on the coexistence of categories in visual representations and highlight the importance of understanding both projected and perceived destination images and how they align.

1. Introduction

Social media has transformed the dynamics of information creation and communication, influencing consumer behaviour, marketing approaches and brand perception (Hays, Page, & Buhalis, 2013). Understanding the role of a destination's image and how it is perceived by guests is an important issue in tourism management that helps the positioning and marketing of a destination. Now that content is no longer provided exclusively by tourism marketers, travellers are able to find out more about travel destinations and products. Today, users are drawing attention to destinations just as much as tourism organisations and creative user-generated content (UGC) about tourism regions is steadily increasing. Visual content is particularly important in the tourism industry relying on delivering visual cues stimulating visitor's imagination and motivation (Ye & Tussyadiah, 2011). Recent research shows the pivotal role of destinations online image, reflecting the nuanced perspectives of tourists who emphasize the importance of both official and user-generated content in shaping destination brand credibility (Jiménez-Barreto, Rubio, Campo, & Molinillo, 2020). Hence, it is crucial for Destination Management Organisations (DMOs) to understand how tourists perceive the destination, enabling the development of effective marketing campaigns. Despite the recognition of the importance of visual content in tourism industry, destination marketing scholars mainly analyse visuals created by tourists (Acuti, Mazzoli,

Donvito, & Chan, 2018) separately from DMOs (Yu, Xie, & Wen, 2020) on social media platforms.

To close this research gap and to generate a better understanding of how the perceived destination image of UGC aligns with the intended destination image projected by DMOs and tourism service providers, this study focuses on the specific case of the tourism region Lake Lucerne in Switzerland and its presentation on the popular social media platform Instagram. Its central to identify and analyse the most critical attributes by comparing visual content on Instagram, contributing to a more granular understanding of the elements shaping the destination image of the alpine region Lake Lucerne.

Instagram is a web and mobile social media application (app) that prospers through the participation of its users. The app's focus is to encourage interaction and creative expression among users who share aesthetically pleasing visual content within the digital community (Leaver, Highfield, & Abidin, 2020). The platform's continuing popularity across DMOs and tourists (Kepios, 2022) made it a comprehensive choice, ensuring a representative analysis of projected and perceived destination image.

The research objective results from a transdisciplinary approach and was formulated jointly with the region's tourism stakeholders as part of a previous applied research project on data cooperation (Geyer, Stuber-Berries, Liebrich, & Wyss, 2021). The data within this project is proprietary, owned by the collaborating partners. However, this

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research relies on visuals from Instagram, which are accessible through the social network platform. The primary objective is to gain practical insights for collaborative tourism marketing in the region which is based on academic findings. Against this background this study highlights the Lake Lucerne region which is a typical lake and mountain region in Switzerland. The insights from this investigation will be valuable for the Lake Lucerne region and for similar alpine regions.

2. Literature review

2.1. Destination image's impact on tourism

The influence of destination image and perception and its effect on consumer decision-making was introduced in the 1970s (Crompton, 1979; Hunt, 1975) and has since then been one of the most researched tourism topics (Stepchenkova & Mills, 2010). The substantial body of literature includes studies from various disciplines (Gallarza, Saura, & García, 2002) addressing questions regarding destination branding (Qu, Kim, & Im, 2011; Sahin & Baloglu, 2011), influence on decision-making of tourists (Girish, Park, & Lee, 2021; Lee, 2009; Tavitiyaman & Qu, 2013), intention to revisit (Loi, So, Lo, & Fong, 2017) and many other aspects. Destination image thus influences tourist behaviour before, during, and after travel, as it is an important instrument which contributes to tourists' loyalty. However, there is no consensus in the academic community on a methodological framework to categorize and evaluate destination image (Picazo & Moreno-Gil, 2019). As illustrated in the recent literature review by Afshardoost and Eshaghi (2020), conceptually there are different image dimensions such as overall, cognitive, affective, and conative image identified and various studies that define the destination image from an uni- to a multidimensional construct depending on the research purpose.

2.2. The role of social media

Therefore, the conceptual vagueness (Gallarza et al., 2002; Lai & Li, 2016; Tasci, Gartner, & Tamer Cavusgil, 2007) and also new communication tools such as social media still prompt new research avenues. Recent studies have focused on online destination image formation (He, Deng, Li, & Gu, 2022; Lojo, Li, & Xu, 2020; Y. Sun, Liang, & Chang, 2020), highlighting the advantages of social media in allowing travellers to actively engage in information search and trip planning (Buhalis & Law, 2008; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010), as well as influencing the decision-making process (Hudson & Thal, 2013). Nowadays tourists play a leading role in the projection of a destination's image by sharing their experiences and opinions, contributing to the formation of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) communication (Camprubi, Guia, & Comas, 2013). An extensive review on the influence of social networks on WOM through creation and fast dissemination of user-generated content (UGC) in hospitality and tourism can be found in Chen and Law (2016). Image-sharing social media platforms, such as Instagram, serve as a valuable source of information and evaluation for tourists, providing them with benefits in terms of accessing relevant and current content (ELTayeb, 2021). Additionally, Sheldon and Bryant (2016) reveal that individuals with active social lifestyles are highly motivated to use Instagram for documenting their travel experiences. The platform's role in promoting destination experiences becomes apparent, as tourists utilize Instagram to share their travel stories and memories. Consequently, the influence of Instagram on the destination image becomes evident, as the experiences shared by users can contribute to shaping the perception of the destination. Furthermore restrictions on social media use (Yi & Dallen, 2021) or inaccurate promotional information about the destinations have a detrimental impact on tourists' perception of a destination and can result in tourist negative evaluations (Li, He, Li, Huang, & Liu, 2023).

Against the background of the tourist's view, it also gives new opportunities to the destination management organisations (DMOs) and

the tourism service providers (e.g. accommodations, restaurants, mountain railways) that are responsible for creating and communicating these destination images to tourists and thus, promote and position the destination in the tourism market. The impact of social media has been topic of various studies in the last decade (Hudson & Thal, 2013) more specifically on city branding (Acuti et al., 2018) or the impact of colour on destination branding (Yu et al., 2020), co-creation space for tourist destination image-building (Iglesias-Sánchez, Correia, Jambrino-Maldonado, & las Heras-Pedrosa, 2020), visitor monitoring (Tenkanen et al., 2017).

2.3. Perceived and projected destination image

There is an important distinction to be made between the destination image perceived by tourists (Tasci et al., 2007; Zhang, Fu, Cai, & Lu, 2014) and the projected image of the tourism destination (Picazo & Moreno-Gil, 2019). The literature is more strongly focused on the perceived destination image which has also been regularly reviewed and conceptualized whereas the projected destination image has received less attention (Camprubi, Guia, & Comas, 2014). Picazo and Moreno-Gil (2019) focus in their review therefore on the destination's projected image on photographs through which characteristics, concepts and values are transmitted for marketing purposes. Understanding both sides, the perceived image and the projected identity allows to analyse the consistency between the two. Obtaining a good alignment between the projected and perceived image of the destination has become a key objective (W. Sun, Tang, & Liu, 2021). In terms of destination image research, the increasingly shared user-generated content allows researchers to get a better understanding of tourists' perception and gives an opportunity to compare this to the projected image from the destinations. The discrepancy between these two remain still unclear and are crucial to be better understood as it can lead to tourist confusion (W. Sun et al., 2021). There are only a handful of studies comparing these two types of destination image on a specific destination based on different online sources. For example, Mak (2017) compared the perceived image through blog posts and the projected through online content generated by the national tourism organisation (NTO) in Eastern Taiwan. Several important destination image dimensions were under-represented in the NTO content, for example, 'food and beverages', 'transportation', 'information and accommodation'. Marine-Roig and Ferrer-Rosell (2018) also researched three information sources regarding different destination image representation: induced (Catalan Tourist Board), autonomous (Lonely Planet travel guide), and organic (online travel reviews). They found as well that the organic (perceived) image is far different from autonomous and induced (projected) images. A recent study by Wacker and Groth (2020) more specifically looked at the potential image gap on Instagram.

This study aims to build on this body of literature by filling the identified gaps, regarding the alignment of perceived and projected destination image on the case of Lake Lucerne Region in Switzerland. Based on various stakeholder cooperation projects in the region, the joint presentation on social media becomes an increasing interest. Opposed to the situation analysed in Tyrol by Wacker and Groth (2020) the positioning and marketing of the studied region is not yet uniform. This means for example, that there are several destinations with their own management organisation and key stakeholders that form the entire region. Even though the DMO Lucerne Tourism overtakes a guiding role, the projection of the destination image is still multifaceted. To give a concrete example, there is no unifying but several hashtags such as #lakelucerne region or #myLucerne used to promote the region.

Against this background, this explorative study is a comparative analysis of multiple destinations in the Lake Lucerne Region, which compares the projected destination image of the tourism region around Lake Lucerne with the user generated content of this region. The main objective is to determine the most important attributes representing the destination by comparing visual Instagram content of the Lake Lucerne

Region, presented on major accounts of tourism stakeholders of the region (projected destination image) and on private accounts who visit the region (perceived destination image). The goal is to determine similarities and differences in the attributes used to visualize the destination image and establish strategic implications. The following research questions are proposed:

- What are the main attributes representing the projected and perceived destination image of Lake Lucerne Region on Instagram?
- Are there important differences between the destination image projected by major tourism organisations and service providers and the destination image perceived by tourists?
- What are possible strategic implications for an overall social media marketing of the Lake Lucerne Region regarding main attributes representing the destination image?

This explorative study builds on key questions posed by tourism practitioners from a recently completed applied research project of the Lake Lucerne Region, addressing the difficulties of a collaborative approach to social media marketing within a fragmented the tourism region.

3. Materials and methods

Our study is primarily centred around visual analysis, with a specific focus on gaining insights from posts shared by both users and DMOs on Instagram. This approach allows us to examine the perceived and predicted image of users and DMOs based exclusively on the visual content of their posts. The methodology of this study is based on the comparative content analysis proposed by [Stepchenkova and Zhan \(2013\)](#), which has already been applied by [Wacker and Groth \(2020\)](#) to Tyrol, and is now exploratively applied to the Lake Lucerne Region to expand on this stream of research. They built the basis of the attribute classification of the visual data in this study. In the first step of the analysis, a pre-test with a limited sample size was conducted. The results were then

discussed with different experts before analysing a bigger sample in a second step. In a third step, the co-occurrence of the categories was analysed for the bigger sample.

The research is not without limitations. The potential subjectivity of the analysis was taken into consideration. Therefore, the analysis of the data as well as the interpretative conclusions are shown in a plausible and comprehensible way. Additionally, a three-step pre-test of the attribute category using alternative interpretations which included different reading styles of four independent researchers took place ([Fig. 1](#)). Thus, a consensual validation and intersubjectivity could be established.

3.1. Data collection and selection

The data basis for this study is the visual content posted on Instagram on the tourism region. The first step was to define the data to be selected. The projected image is represented by the posts of the Instagram accounts of the main DMO representing the region, Lucerne Tourism, and key points of interests (POI) attracting tourists to the region like mount Rigi, mount Pilatus and the Lake Lucerne represented by the Lake Lucerne Navigation Company. This selection reflects the project partners of the former applied research project on data cooperation in the region ([Geyer et al., 2021](#)). Therefore, the basis of the projected image was chosen to be the four Instagram accounts of these tourism actors ([Table 1](#)). Due to the relatively small number of posts from the accounts for projected destination image, all posts available on these accounts were selected (2583 posts).

The perceived image is represented by specific hashtags travellers of the region use in their Instagram posts. As there is not one specific hashtag representing the entire region, a selection had to be defined. Only hashtags in English were considered to include posts by both, Swiss and foreign tourists. A comparison of the most frequent hashtags with the primary hashtags used by the tourism organisations led to the final selection of the hashtags used to represent the tourists' perspective in the present analysis ([Table 2](#)). The number of selected posts per hashtag

Fig. 1. Illustration pre-test phase and roll-out.

Table 1
Projected destination image: data basis.

Selected tourism providers -Projected destination image	Respective Instagram account name	No. of posts ^a	Timeline	
			First post retrieved	Last post retrieved
Regional DMO: Lucerne Tourism	ilove_lucerne	473	12.04.2016	18.11.2021
POI: mount Pilatus	pilatus	607	25.11.2016	17.11.2021
POI: mount Rigi	rigi.ch	1100	28.06.2013	19.11.2021
POI: Lake Lucerne Navigation Company	vierwaldstättersee_lucerne	403	10.03.2017	17.11.2021
Total number of posts		2583		

^a at the time of analysis in November 2021.

Table 2
Perceived destination image: data basis.

Selected hashtags -Perceived destination image	No. of total posts per hashtag ^a	Selected number of posts	Timeline	
			First post retrieved	Last post retrieved
#lucerne	~835,000	1659	10.05.2021	19.11.2021
#pilatus	~282,000	2169	08.05.2021	16.11.2021
#rigi	~162,000	1977	26.01.2021	17.11.2021
#lakelucerne	~152,000	1241	25.04.2021	18.11.2021
#mylucerne	~42,000	2772	01.06.2021	19.11.2021
#lakelucerne_region	~21,000	2095	08.08.2020	17.11.2021
Total number of posts		11,913		

^a at the time of analysis in November 2021.

depends on the number of available posts (i.e. Instagram limits the number of posts that can be scrolled back in time) and the timeframe between the first and the last available post (which depends on the frequencies with which the hashtags are used and on the number of available posts per hashtag). The timeframe between June and November 2021 was identified as the timeframe for which there were posts available for all hashtags. The objective entailed achieving a balanced selection of posts throughout the designated time frame. The chosen time frame was deliberately selected to align, to a reasonable extent, with all the hashtags under consideration. For the more frequent hashtags, only every fourth or fifth post was selected. No weights were used for the selection since it is unknown who the users of the different hashtags are and how the usage developed over time. Overall, 11,913 posts were selected representing the perceived destination image.

For all the selected posts, the name of the account, the date, the link to the picture or video, the caption and the number of likes, views and comments were scraped and saved into ten separate spreadsheets. The data scraping took place mid-November, hence the posts of the selected hashtags date back from then until sometime between January and August, depending on the popularity of hashtag. The data scraping was conducted by an independent third party using Phyton and the Selenium library to gather the data from Instagram. The collected data was organized for subsequent analysis. Throughout this process, ethical guidelines were followed to respect users' privacy, and ensuring compliance with Instagram's terms of service.

3.2. Data cleaning

The present analysis focuses on the projected and perceived image of the Lake Lucerne Region based on the pictures used in Instagram posts. Therefore, all posts containing videos or reels were deleted from the dataset of the accounts. No further cleaning of the projected destination image dataset was necessary, and 2393 posts were used for the analysis. To ensure a clean dataset for the perceived destination image, some more steps were needed. First, posts from the above selected accounts representing the projected destination image using one of the hashtags were deleted from the dataset. Second, all posts for which the account name related to suppliers of touristic products or services (hotels, tour operators, etc), companies in general or obvious fake accounts were

removed. A review of the #pilatus posts showed that many users did not use this hashtag with a touristic intention (i.e. to refer to the mount Pilatus) but rather to planes and the namesake Pilatus Aircraft Ltd. Such posts were removed as well as they are not relevant to the touristic destination image. Third, as in the projected dataset only picture-posts were kept, and videos or reels were deleted. And finally, all posts that were significantly older than the rest (collected from the most popular posts rather than from the most recent ones) were deleted to keep all the posts in about the same time range. Subsequently, 7994 posts remained in the cleaned dataset. Posts in which more than one of the selected hashtags are used, were flagged but not excluded (Table 3).

3.3. Analysis

3.3.1. Pre-test

For the pre-test analysis (see Fig. 1), a random sample of 20 posts per account and hashtag was drawn. This corresponds to 80 posts (4 accounts) for the projected image and 120 posts (6 hashtags) for the perceived image. In total three researchers assigned the pictures to different categories, according to the attributes on the pictures using consensual coding method. Consensual coding helps to ensure that the interpretations and categorisations is a result of collective agreement, reducing the potential for bias or subjectivity in the analysis (Kuckartz, 2014).

In this study, a combined deductive-inductive approach was employed, entailing a deductive analysis rooted in the categories outlined by Wacker and Groth (2020). The categories used by Wacker and Groth (2020) are: 'Nature & Landscapes', 'People', 'Plants', 'Architecture & Buildings', 'Resident's Lives', 'Outdoor & Adventure', 'Tourism Offers & Facilities', 'Food & Drinks', 'Country Landscapes', 'Leisure Activities', 'Transport & Infrastructure', 'Urban Landscapes', 'Art Objects', 'Domesticated Animals', 'Festivals & Rituals', 'Wildlife', 'Traditional Clothing', 'Historical Sites'. The mentioned categories from Wacker and Groth (2020) contain many similarities to the Lake Lucerne Region as both Tyrol and the Lake Lucerne Region are Alpine destinations with a focus on landscape and mountains. However, the dominant lake in the Lake Lucerne Region exhibits a main difference.

Simultaneously, a second researcher instructed to classify the pictures according to categories she considered appropriate, performed independently an inductive classification. It allowed to include a different perspective and ensure the selection of categories considers all relevant aspects for the image presentation in the Lake Lucerne Region.

The two randomly selected picture samples of 80 (projected) and 120 (perceived) categorised by the two separate researchers showed an overlap of 79%. Consequent to this initial analysis of independent coding, a third researcher was engaged to facilitate the integration of both deductive and inductive codes in collaboration with the first and the second researcher. Following these two classifications, categories were compared, added, or merged where necessary. After discussing their coding, they reached consensus in the most appropriate coding.

The third researchers then reviewed all the deviating classifications to ensure a consistent handling of the categories. In instances of divergent classifications, such as whether to categorize a meadow under 'Plants' or 'Nature & Landscapes (other)' and determining if a cableway

Table 3
Posts referring to more than one of the selected hashtags.

	#lucerne	#pilatus	#rigi	#lakelucerne	#mylucerne	#lakelucerneregion
#lucerne		15	15	61	56	24
#pilatus	15		21	31	44	25
#rigi	15	21		29	26	33
#lakelucerne	61	31	29		94	73
#mylucerne	56	44	26	94		443
#lakelucerneregion	24	25	33	73	443	

Table 4
Overview - Descriptions of the categories used to classify pictures.

Category	Description
People	Human, Body parts
Mountain	Mountains, Mountain landscapes in the highlands
Lake	Lakes, Rivers
Nature & Landscapes (other)	Green landscapes, Meadows, Mountain landscapes
Plants	Trees, Flowers, Plants, Forest
Wildlife	Wild animals
Domesticated Animals	Domestic animals
Boat	Boats & Cruises
Railway/cableway	Railways, Cable cars, Cogwheel railroad, Train
Transport & Infrastructure (other)	Tracks, Train station, Airport, Mountain station
Architecture & Buildings	Buildings, Houses, Special architectures, Villages, Restaurants
Historical Sites	Historic sights
Urban Landscapes	Urban landscapes
Spring	Spring, Blooming flowers
Summer	Summer, Lots of sun, Green mountains
Fall	Autumn, Colourful leaves
Winter/Snow	Winter, Snow
Sun	Sunrise/set, Sun
Night	Night, Dark, Stars
Outdoor & Adventure	Outdoor, Sports, Adventure, People
Leisure Activities	Leisure activities, Paragliding, Hiking
Tourism Offers & Facilities	Tourism activities, Active people, Mountain, Boat, Railway
Foods & Drinks	Food, Drinks, Tableware
Art Objects	Paintings, Art, Objects, Images
Resident's Lives	Locals, Daily life
Festivals & Rituals	Swiss traditions, Festivals
Other	Other

station should be coded as ‘Railway/cableway’ or ‘Transport & Infrastructure (other)’, discrepancies were resolved through collaborative discussions among the research team. These discussions led to specific clarifications: meadows were clarified as falling under ‘Nature & Landscapes (other)’, when considering the entire landscape, whereas a single flower was coded as ‘Plants’. Similarly, for cableway stations, the code ‘Railway/cableway’ was refined to encompass only the vehicles themselves, distinguishing them from the infrastructure elements, which were coded as ‘Transport & Infrastructure (other)’. This iterative and collaborative process (Kuckartz, 2014) ensured precise and consistent coding, addressing incongruities, and enhancing the reliability of the classification system.

The categories provided by Wacker and Groth (2020) were complemented by 11 categories that allows to better portray the particular situation at Lake Lucerne. Two original categories were omitted as they did not appear in the visuals (‘Mountain’, ‘Lake, Plants’, ‘Nature & Landscapes (other)’, ‘Wildlife’, ‘Domesticated Animals’, ‘Boat, Railway/cableway’, ‘Transport & Infrastructure (other)’, ‘Architecture & Buildings’, ‘Historical Sites’, ‘Urban Landscapes’, ‘Spring, Summer’, ‘Fall’, ‘Winter/Snow’, ‘Sun’, ‘Night’, ‘Outdoor & Adventure’, ‘Leisure Activities’, ‘Tourism Offers & Facilities’, ‘Foods & Drinks’, ‘Art Objects’, ‘Resident’s Lives’, ‘Festivals & Rituals’, ‘Other’). Finally, a classification system of a total of 27 attribute categories was obtained (Table 7).

3.3.2. Analysis

In the analysis a total of 600 pictures were analysed. This number is large enough to make sound conclusions but still small enough to do it with reasonable effort. In contrast to the pre-test, the number of analysed posts was defined relative to the total number of posts for each hashtag or account in the final dataset. For the perceived destination image, 300 posts correspond to 3.14% of the posts in the dataset. Therefore 3.14% of the posts of each hashtag were analysed (Table 5). For the projected destination image, the share is 11.57% (Table 6). All posts were randomly selected (see Table 9) (see Table 8).

After the final attribute coding, the number of assignments to each category for the two samples were compared. Due to the categorical nature of the variable, a Chi-squared test is used to test for the statistical independence of two random variables. In this case it can be used to test if the number of pictures in a category in the perceived image sample correlates with the number of pictures in the same category in the projected image sample. The hypothesis is therefore as follows:

H0. the distributions of the perceived and the projected image are statistically independent.

For categories including frequencies lower than 5, a Fisher’s exact test is used to verify the result and to calculate the precise p-value. For a deeper analysis of the pictures, the co-occurrences of different categories within the pictures were analysed. This analysis was conducted separately for the perceived and the projected image. Since the categories occur with different frequencies, the numbers are standardized, and the resulting z-scores are compared. The basis for our analysis consisted of the actual frequencies of co-occurrence between categories, such as Boat & Lake in the case of DMO, which occurred 39 times. The independent probability of co-occurrence was calculated based on theoretical probabilities assuming that the categories are independent of each other. These probabilities were derived from the total frequencies of individual categories and multiplied. For example, Boat = 0.07, Lake = 0.47, and their joint probability was calculated as 0.034. The expected frequency was determined by multiplying the number of pictures (300) by the independent probability. For instance, $300 \cdot 0.034 = 10.27$, indicating that Boat & Lake would be expected to appear approximately 10 times. The z-value was calculated based on the observed frequency, expected frequency, and variance of the co-occurrence of categories in the pictures. This statistical measure quantifies the number of standard deviations by which a particular value deviates from the mean. Negative z-values indicate deviations below the mean. While positive z-values indicate deviations above the mean. When the absolute value of the z-value is smaller than 1.96, it suggests a lack of statistical significance

Table 5
Perceived destination image: number of posts selected for the picture analysis.

	No. of posts in final dataset	No. of analysed posts	
#LakeLucerne	1068	34	
#lakelucerneregion	1343	42	
#lucerne	1322	41	
#mylucerne	2247	71	
#pilatus	1793	56	
#rigi	1769	56	
	9542	300	3.14%

Table 6
Projected destination image: number of posts selected for the picture analysis.

	No. of posts in final dataset	No. of analysed posts	
iloveLucerne	473	55	
Pilatus	607	70	
Rigi	1110	128	
vierwaldstaetterseelakelucerne	403	47	
	2593	300	11.57%

and implies independence between the two categories, meaning they are less likely to appear together in a visual. Inverse, z-values greater than 1.96 indicate a substantial departure from independence, suggesting a significant dependence between the two categories and a higher probability of their joint occurrence in a visual. Furthermore, z-values less

Table 7
Projected destination image: descriptive analysis.

Selected tourism providers -Projected destination image	No. of posts	No. of posts with videos/reels	No. of posts with likes	Mean likes	Median likes	No. of posts with comments	Mean no. of comments
ilove_lucerne	473	10	453	1040	896	465	15
pilatus	607	23	561	704	640	586	8
Rigi.ch	1110	61	988	426	395	1071	7
Vierwaldstaettersee lakelucerne	403	6	391	373	333	389	5

Table 8
Perceived destination image: descriptive analysis.

Selected hashtags -Perceived destination image	No. of posts	No. of posts with videos/reels	No. of posts with likes	Mean likes	Median likes	No. of posts with comments	Mean no. of comments
#lakelucerne	1066	48	966	98	36	669	5
#lakelucerneregion	1339	46	1157	257	62	128	8
#lucerne	1313	46	1013	124	27	0	0
#mylucerne	2243	91	1874	154	43	0	0
#pilatus	1788	92	1523	99	41	0	0
#rigi	1764	115	1461	120	33	0	0

Table 9
Frequencies of the categories in the perceived and projected images.

Category	Projected	Projected (%)	Perceived	Perceived (%)	Total	Total (%)	p-value ¹
Plants	201	67%	203	68%	404	67%	
Mountain	227	76%	157	52%	384	64%	0.00000***
Lake	157	52%	140	47%	297	50%	
Nature & Landscapes (other)	157	52%	104	35%	261	44%	0.00000***
Architecture & Buildings	121	40%	106	35%	227	38%	
People	66	22%	92	31%	158	26%	0.01600**
Sun	77	26%	40	13%	117	20%	0.00000***
Winter/Snow	97	32%	19	6%	116	19%	0.00000***
Tourism Offers & Facilities	84	28%	31	10%	115	19%	0.00000***
Transport & Infrastructure (other)	68	23%	33	11%	101	17%	0.00000***
Leisure Activities	35	12%	46	15%	81	14%	
Boat	40	13%	22	7%	62	10%	0.01600**
Historical Sites	18	6%	34	11%	52	9%	0.02000**
Night	29	10%	18	6%	47	8%	0.09500*
Outdoor & Adventure	14	5%	25	8%	39	7%	0.06900*
Urban Landscapes	14	5%	23	8%	37	6%	
Wildlife	18	6%	19	6%	37	6%	
Domesticated Animals	6	2%	26	9%	32	5%	0.00000***
Art Objects	5	2%	19	6%	24	4%	0.00400***
Fall	5	2%	19	6%	24	4%	0.00400***
Other	6	2%	18	6%	24	4%	0.01200**
Foods & Drinks	8	3%	10	3%	18	3%	
Railway/cableway	5	2%	5	2%	10	2%	
Summer	1	0%	4	1%	5	1%	
Resident's Lives	0	0%	3	1%	3	1%	
Festivals & Rituals	2	1%	0	0%	2	0%	
Spring	1	0%	1	0%	2	0%	

¹ p-value of the Chi-square analysis. In case the expected value is smaller or equal to 5, Fisher p-value is shown. Value is only shown if significant. ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

than -1.96 indicate an improbable co-occurrence of the two categories within the same visual.

4. Results

In a first step, a descriptive analysis of all the retrieved posts was conducted to get a better understanding of the dataset. In a second step, a sample of the picture-posts was analysed as described above.

4.1. Descriptive statistics of the selected posts

The number of posts of the four accounts representing the projected destination image vary between 403 and 1110 (see Table 4). However, there are many similarities, the majority of posts contain pictures and only a few videos or reels. This confirms our decision to focus on picture-

posts. In our datafile, there is a variable for the number of likes per post. However, for videos and reels this variable is missing. Therefore, the number of posts with likes can be used as an approximation for the number of picture-posts. Only few posts have not received any likes at all. While the number of total posts by the DMO (ilove_lucerne) is rather small, the average number of likes is much higher than for the posts by the POI. For all four accounts, the median of the number of likes is smaller than the mean which indicates that the likes are not equally distributed over all the posts. Nevertheless, the median shows that there is a significant number of people who see the posts and like them.

The share of posts that receive comments is rather high (>96%) and every post gets on average between 5 and 15 comments. An analysis of the content of the comments is not part of this study.

The perceived image dataset, like the projected dataset, contains only few posts with videos and reels but a high share of picture-posts. The mean and the median of the number of likes as well as the number of posts with comments is lower than for the projected image which indicates a lower average perception of the tourist's posts. The unequal distribution of likes between the posts which is indicated by the median that is smaller than the mean might possibly be explained by the presence of some influencer-posts that get above-average attention.

4.2. Attribute classification of the pictures

All pictures of the selected sample were assigned to at least one and at most eight of the 27 attribute categories, on average 4.9 categories (projected image) and 4.1 categories (perceived image) respectively.

The analysis reveals that the predominant categories (>35%) are 'Plants', 'Mountain', 'Lake', 'Nature & Landscapes (other)' and 'Architecture and Buildings'. This holds true for both the projected and the perceived image sample. The share of pictures classified as plants is approximately the same for both samples accounting for 67% in the projected image sample and 68% in the perceived image sample. However, the other four categories mentioned above, have a much higher share of pictures in the projected image sample compared to the perceived image sample.

Further statistical analysis using Chi-squared statistics indicates, that there is a significant difference between the frequencies of 15 categories between the two samples. For the projected image sample, there are significantly more pictures classified under the categories of 'Mountain', 'Nature & Landscapes (other)', 'Sun', 'Winter/Snow', 'Tourism Offers & Facilities', 'Transport & Infrastructure (other)', 'Boat', 'Night'. On the other hand, the perceived image sample has significantly more pictures classified under the categories of 'People', 'Historical Sites', 'Outdoor & Adventure', 'Domesticated Animals*', 'Art Objects*', 'Fall*', 'Other*' (* = small numbers).

4.3. Co-occurrence of categories in pictures

In the analysis, exploration was conducted into the co-occurrence of categories in pictures, examining a total of 351 possible combinations, whereby each combination has two elements. Z-scores were calculated to determine the likelihood of these combinations. The aggregated map of code-relations from user pictures is presented in Figs. 2 and 3. Only categories with a minimum of 30 co-occurrence or higher are illustrated.

Analysing the category combinations in pictures captured by tourists, 40 likely combinations and 63 unlikely combinations were observed. Fig. 2 provides a graphical depiction of the five categories with the highest degrees of simultaneous occurrence. Conversely Fig. 3 illustrates six categories that exhibit a marked unlikelihood of being conjoined. The lines connecting the different codes (data points) vary in thickness to indicate the intensity as also represented in the numbers connected to the lines.

In the investigation of the category combinations depicted in the visual compositions generated by DMOs and POIs, it has been ascertained that 54 combinations exhibit a substantial likelihood of co-

Fig. 2. Code-Relations user z-value likely combination (min 30).

Fig. 3. Code-Relations User z-value unlikely combination (min 30).

occurrence, while 38 combinations possess a diminished probability. Fig. 4 illustrates a visual representation of the categories that have a high probability of cooccurring in a single picture from the DMO dataset. In contrast, the categories 'Lake & People' with 30(-2.132), as well as 'People & Plants' with 33(-4.165) are unlikely to occur together. However, due to small sample sizes in some cases, no meaningful conclusions could be drawn.

5. Discussion

Our findings support the notion that destination image plays a crucial role in influencing tourist behaviour before, during, and after travel, contributing to tourists' inspiration. The results of our study provide valuable insights into the descriptive statistics of the selected posts and the attribute classification of the pictures, shedding light on the co-occurrence of categories in pictures.

The selected posts showed variations in numbers among the four accounts representing the projected destination image. Picture-posts were more common than videos or reels, supporting our focus on them for analysis. Likes served as an approximation of picture-post numbers, with minimal posts receiving no likes, indicating viewer interaction and attention. DMO posts received higher average likes than POI posts, indicating greater engagement. Uneven distribution of likes across posts suggests varying levels of attention. These findings emphasize the significance of the projected image in capturing attention and influencing perception.

The descriptive statistics of the selected posts reveal the significant interaction and attention from users, as indicated by the number of likes received. This aligns with studies highlighting the advantages of social media platforms, such as Instagram, in allowing travellers to actively engage in information search and trip planning (Buhalis & Law, 2008; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010), as well as influencing their decision-making process (Hudson & Thal, 2013). The active role of tourists in shaping

Fig. 4. Code-Relations DMO/POI z-value likely combination (min 30).

the destination image through sharing experiences and opinions on social media platforms reinforces the formation of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) communication (Camprubí et al., 2013). The influence of Instagram as an image-sharing platform becomes evident, as tourists utilize it to share their travel stories and memories, contributing to the shaping of destination perception (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016).

Moving on to the attribute classification of the pictures, it was found that all pictures in the selected sample were assigned to at least one and at most eight of the 27 attribute categories. On average, the projected image contained pictures classified under 4.9 categories, while the perceived image had an average of 4.1 categories. One possible explanation for this difference is that tourism organisations aim to include as many touristic attributes as possible in their pictures, whereas tourists tend to focus on fewer aspects that they are currently experiencing.

The attribute classification of the pictures demonstrates the presence of specific categories that dominate both the projected and perceived image samples. The prevalence of categories such as Plants, Mountain, Lake, Nature & Landscapes (other), and Architecture and Buildings aligns with the existing literature on destination image dimensions. These categories reflect the iconic and picturesque features often associated with tourist destinations. The similarity in the share of pictures classified as plants in both samples suggests consistency in the representation of natural elements, which is in line with the literature emphasizing the importance of nature and landscapes in destination imagery.

The theoretical background emphasizes the significance of understanding both the projected and perceived destination image and their alignment. The study contributes to this understanding by providing insights into the content characteristics and preferences of tourists, as well as the influence of destination organisations in shaping the projected image. The discrepancy between the projected and perceived image samples underscores the need for further research to explore and bridge the gaps between these two aspects.

6. Conclusion and future research

6.1. Theoretical conclusions

Instagram and other social media platforms are highly relevant for the inspiration and information phase of the customer journey. They possess immense potential in visually persuading travellers to explore destinations. Consequently, it becomes crucial for DMOs to consider the perspectives of their visitors when promoting touristic scenes, products, and destinations. This can be achieved by considering the pictures shared by the tourists, since they vary in the composition. Social media enables travellers to create their own presentation of a destination and therefore enhances the marketing activities of a DMO. This research contributes to existing knowledge in several ways. It compares the pictures presented by DMOs and tourists to get useful insights in the similarities and differences. The attributes used for this study have been used before and are adapted to the specific context of the tourism region Lake Lucerne to replicate the findings in a different destination. Furthermore, this study extends the existing research which focuses mainly on the tourists' (Acuti et al., 2018) or the DMOs' (Yu et al., 2020) perspective but not both. The present study provides insights into the composition of the pictures used (1) by the DMO and POI of the Lake Lucerne region representing their touristic offers and (2) by the tourists sharing their experiences in this region. The pictures posted by the DMO and POI combine more categories than those posted by the tourists since they focus on the presentation of the diversity of their offers while tourists rather illustrate their specific experience. These findings cannot answer the question whether DMOs are expected to use pictures composed of several touristic offers or rather more experience-focused pictures such as those posted by the tourists. There is still a gap in researching the most effective composition of pictures.

6.2. Managerial conclusions

The analysis reveals a remarkable similarity between the projected and perceived images, which is an encouraging result for those responsible for the projected image. Despite the region's heterogeneity and the absence of a unique hashtag representing the entire region, this

alignment suggests that the tourist organisations responsible for the projected image should regularly verify their posts and ensure that this coherence can be maintained.

Misconceptions may arise regarding the necessity for a DMO to post pictures on Instagram and actively advertise itself when users undertake these actions in concordance with the DMO. However, it is important for the DMO to maintain an active presence on Instagram as it plays a crucial role in ensuring visibility and stimulating the inspiration of prospective travellers. Relying solely on user-generated content exposes the DMO to potential risks. The presence of fraudulent accounts operated by users, which inaccurately represent the region, poses a notable concern. This absence of authenticity and limited control over content dissemination can result in a distorted portrayal of the destination, deviating from the intended positioning envisaged by the DMO. Therefore, it is imperative for the DMO to actively participate in the content generation and promotion process to mitigate such risks and ensure the preservation of the desired destination image. Furthermore, the establishment of an official DMO account on Instagram facilitates linkages and tagging, enabling users to access official and reliable information sources. It is likely that tourists do have different expectations of the pictures posted by a DMO or a POI than of those posted by other tourists. Nevertheless, it might be interesting for a DMO to test what kind of pictures are better received by the tourists. Another possibility is an enrichment of the official DMO account with pictures previously shared by tourists to combine the presentation of offers with real experiences.

6.3. Social conclusions

It is to be expected that different focal points of different sender such as beautiful individual elements and a self-presentation or an overall view do have a different influence on the perception of the image of a destination by the tourists. A growing availability of user generated content might thus influence the perception of a destination. DMO need to be aware of potential gaps in the representation of the destination. Pictures may not always resonate on a personal level with potential tourists. Image editing, special camera techniques, camera angles and emphasizing the best aspects of a destination could let the pictures appear as high-quality, professional, and staged, which casts doubt on their authenticity. In contrast pictures posted by the tourists reflect their individual experiences and might thus meet the expectations of future tourists by being relatable since they show authenticity. It is therefore important for the DMO to keep their pictures authentic.

Another positive effect of authentic posts could be their influence of the behavior of future tourists. If they see for example nice and clean meadows and lakes, they might be willing to adapt their behavior and contribute to the maintenance of such a surrounding by avoiding littering.

Many visitors of the region Lake Lucerne have an international background. Their pictures posted on social media are therefore not only a presentation of their own perception of the destination but also a contribution to a broader understanding of different cultures. A global audience with various cultural backgrounds gets in touch with these pictures and share them among several societies. This process can promote appreciation as well as different perspectives on the destination which enhances the marketing activities of the DMO.

Nevertheless, it is essential to adopt a critical perspective because the form of communication about a destination has consequences. A DMO or POI can only influence the image transmitted by their own pictures and information. They usually pursue a marketing strategy that focuses on the main attractions and neglects out-of-the-ordinary places. However, the communication by tourists fosters greater engagement by covering a broader spectrum of experiences captures in pictures. This diversity can appeal to tourists looking for unique places and has the potential to create new hotspots by influencing travel decisions and preferences. This in turn has consequences for the local population, such as over tourism, which might not be intended. It is thus important for the DMO

to not only rely on pictures posted by the tourists and to develop counterstrategies if necessary.

6.4. Future research

Another insight gained from the analysis is that an average picture of the DMO and POI is composed of more attributes than a tourists' average picture. This observation raises the question of interdependencies between the categories. Further research should investigate and visually represent correlations of different categories to provide a deeper understanding of typical composition of a picture used to project the destinations' image and to the one perceived by tourists. Such insights can help DMO to improve their strategic online marketing. Against this background it becomes relevant to explore the possibility of a homogenization process within the visual depiction of destinations on Instagram. An exploration of this phenomenon can entail investigating whether there exists a discernible tendency of certain types of pictures to gain dominance, possibly resulting in a convergence of visual content across diverse users and destinations. Furthermore, examining the extent to which travellers influence each other in terms of content creation and selection on Instagram is crucial, including patterns of imitation, inspiration, and interaction.

A consequent analysis could focus on conducting comparative analyses across multiple destinations to gain further insights in the interaction between projected and perceived destination image. This will facilitate understanding of any commonalities or differences in image portrayal across country borders. Thereby the available data could be used to compare the results focussing on specific types of posts such as those with the highest number of likes. Also, the content of the caption, could be analysed and used to gain more specific insights. Additionally, an analysis of photographs in consideration of amateur and professional photography regarding camera techniques, authenticity, virality, shareability and repost of the visual elements can be considered.

As new social media platforms emerge where users, tourism organisations, and providers can post and share audio-visual content, it becomes imperative to include these platforms in research efforts. Investigating their impact on destination image perception will provide invaluable insights.

This study's observations are limited to Instagram and may not fully represent other social media platforms such as Snapchat or TikTok.

By exploring these areas, future research can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of travel photography visual content creation, distribution, and perception both on Instagram but also across various social media platforms. This expanded knowledge will help DMOs make informed decisions and develop effective strategies for engaging with their target group.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Carolyn Geyer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Luzia Zimmermann:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Melanie Wyss:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Conceptualization.

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